

TABLE I. ARCHITECTURE TACTICS AND THEIR RELATED TERMS

Tactic name	Related terms
Heartbeat	heartbeat, ping, ping/echo, beat, decorator, piggybacking, outbound, period
Audit trail	audit, trail, wizard, log, string, category, thread
Resource pooling	pooling, pool, thread, connect, sparrow, processor, worker, time-wait, prototype, singleton, strategy, chain of responsibility, lazy load, static scheduling, dynamic priority scheduling
Authentication	authentic, credential, challenge, login
Scheduling	FIFO, fixed-priority, dynamic priority scheduling, schedule, task, priority, adaptor, bridge, composite, flyweight, memento, observer, proxy, strategy
Checkpoint	checkpoint, checkpoints, barrier, weak point
Rollback	layoff, restraint, austerity, abridgement, deliver
Spare	spare, unoccupied, option, unused, logging, minutes
Redundancy replication	redundancy replication, redundancy storage, zone-redundant, geo-redundant, replication
Voting	voting, vote, balloting, choosing, voter, processor, preferred
Shadow operation	shadow operation, shadow mode
Secure session	secure session, security, removal
Time out	time out, run out, constraint, action, monitor, timer, runtime
Time stamp	time stamp, timestamp, time strap
Sanity checking	sanity checking, sanity check
Functional redundancy	functional redundancy, function requirement allocation
Analytical redundancy	parallel, separate, warm restart, dual redundancy
Resisting attacks	resisting attacks, detecting, detect, recovering, recover, sensor, authenticate, confidentiality, exposure, limit access, passwords, one-time passwords, digital certificates
Maintain data confidentiality	maintain data confidentiality, handle, protecting, routine, storage, mandatory
Recovering from attacks	recovering from attacks, state, maintain, maintaining, redundant, access control, profile